

THE NEED TO PRESERVE THE ATMOSPHERE OF SOLIDARITY BETWEEN NATIONS FROM THE INFLUENCE OF DESTRUCTIVE IDEAS

Khalikov Lazizjon Mahmud ugli

Researcher at Bukhara State University

Abstract: This article highlights the need to preserve the atmosphere of interethnic and interethnic harmony from the influence of religious extremism and terrorism, as well as various destructive ideas.

Keywords: religious extremism, terrorism, ideological immunity, indifference, freedom of conscience, law.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan on December 20, 2022, dwelled on the issue of protecting our people from the influence of various destructive ideas and emphasized the following: extremism, terrorism, human trafficking, drug addiction, unfortunately, will not bypass us. But I repeat, in our land, where such great scientists as Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Imam Moturidi, who taught the Muslim Ummah, grew up, can there be people who are lost in this regard, devoted to the ideas of radicalism and extremism? We will not allow any radicalization in our society, the poisoning of the minds of our youth with destructive foreign ideas, the use of religion for political purposes, the substitution of ignorance for enlightenment.” [1].

The moral harm of terrorism lies in the fact that, along with the physical destruction of people, it can introduce a large part of the population into a state of mental paralysis. As a result of emotions such as fear, horror and confusion, people can fall into a state of doubt and doubt about everything, lose confidence in themselves. Just as weapons of mass destruction are terrible in terms of physical losses, terrorism is a terrible weapon that paralyzes people spiritually. [2].

Religious extremism, propaganda of militancy, false religious beliefs, fanaticism, international terrorism, drug trafficking, illegal arms trade are the organizational foundations of inhumane, alien ideas. Through them they realize their evil intentions.

There are various factors that prevent the influence of destructive ideas. This is done primarily due to the human factor. The richness of the spiritual world of a person gives him the opportunity to understand the difference between ideas. Strengthens ideological immunity. Ways to prevent harmful ideas in the technologies of propaganda of the national idea are defined as follows:

- Ensuring healthy upbringing of young people in the family;
- Strengthening the citizens' faith in the foundations of the national idea;
- try to live with national pride and honor;
- to bring up a harmonious generation in all respects;
- Increasing ideological immunity;
- Formation of trust in the national idea in the minds of citizens.

To achieve these negative vices, such as indifference and indifference, boasting, flattery, envy, vanity, disregard for truth, familiarity, parochialism, careerism and self-interest, which are negative states, are contrary to the promotion of the national idea: each of us needs to learn from ourselves[3]. In this sense, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev says: "I need real patriots." [4]

Our state has created all the conditions for various religious organizations to carry out their activities and actively participate in the life of the country. In particular, it is appropriate to note such events as the organization by the Muslim Board of Uzbekistan of spiritual and educational programs on central television, large-scale celebration of conferences dedicated to the birthdays of famous religious figures. However, despite the opportunities created, it is a pity that some religious movements that abused the tolerance of our people worked not only for religious ideas and beliefs, but also for political and extremist goals.

For our people, who have been practicing the Hanafi school for many centuries, they show disrespect for those who worship according to the Hanafi school, insult the scientists of this school, accuse people of infidelity who do not follow the rules of religion, argue with imams, there have been cases such as imitation of representatives of other sects .

A large amount of religious literature from foreign countries, which promotes religious fanaticism and instills fear and panic in people, is distributed among the population by such extremist groups as Hizbut-Tahrir, Akromia, Tavba, Adolat Yushmasa and Stability. countries began to show shares aimed at the mortgage. At the same time, missionary efforts began to penetrate into our country in various ways, the main goal of which was to divide the nation and society along religious lines. The absence in the legislation of our republic of a sufficient legal barrier for missionary activity could have had irreparably grave consequences. Such cases required a revision of the Law on Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations [5].

On July 6, 2021, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations” came into force [6]. This law consists of 35 articles, and when developing this law, the specific conditions of our country, the rights and interests of the people living in it, and the mentality were taken into account. The main purpose of the law is to ensure freedom of conscience and the right to religious beliefs of every person, ensuring the equality of citizens regardless of their attitude to religion, as well as regulating relations related to the activities of religious organizations.

In general, globalization, including the globalization of terrorism, is like a widespread infectious disease that occurs in one place and spreads only in those places where timely measures against it are not taken. The globalization of terrorism in most cases occurs in individual countries with extreme conflicts. At the same time, international terrorism is acquiring world significance as a global problem due to the level of its danger.

In such a tense situation, we need to preserve in our country an atmosphere of peace and tranquility, harmony between citizens and peoples. In particular, we must consider protecting the hearts and minds of our children from evil dangers as the most urgent task [7].

At present, when the struggle for the mind and soul of a person is intensifying, it is necessary to pay attention to the following important tasks in the fight against international terrorism:

Firstly, religious extremism, fanaticism and terrorist acts taking place today in different countries of the world show that neither religion nor nation chooses, they are the enemies of all mankind, the fight against which is an important task and duty not only of the world community, but also directly the state and people of Uzbekistan must be introduced into the minds of our citizens that;

Secondly, it is necessary to bring to the consciousness of every citizen that international terrorism is one of the most negative phenomena of the era, which literally contradicts the strategic goals of our national independence, state sovereignty and democratic development of our country.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning 2022-yil 20 dekabrda Oliy Majlis va O'zbekiston xalqiga Murojaatnomasi.
2. Nigora Safarova. Terrorizm (tarixiy-falsafiy tahlil).-T.:”Noshir” 2009 - B.192
3. B.To'ychiyev I.Ergashev, O.Muxammadiyeva, M.Xo'jaev. Milliy g'oya: O'zbekistonni rivojlantirish strategiyasi. -T.:”Innovatsiya-ziyo”. 2020. -B.156-157.
4. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisiga murojaatnomasi.Toshkent, 2017.
5. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga murojaatnomasini o'rganish va keng jamoatchilik o'rtasida targ'ib etishga bag'ishlangan ilmiy-ommabop qo'llanma. -T.:”Ma'naviyat”2019. -B.267-268

6. O'zbekiston Respublikasining 05.07.2021 yildagi "Vijdon erkinligi va diniy tashkilotlar to'g'risida"gi 699-sonli qonuni. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5491534>

7. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev. Milliy taraqqiyot yo'limizni qat'iyat bilan davom ettirib, yangi bosqichga ko'taramiz. 1-tom., 349-bet –Toshkent-“O'zbekiston” 2019.

8. Xoliqov L. YANGI O'ZBEKISTONNING TARAQQIYOT STRATEGIYASIDA MILLATLARARO TOTUVLIK MUHITINI MUSTAHKAMLASH ZARURATI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2022. – Т. 9.

9. Xoliqov L. O'ZBEKISTONDA MILLATLARARO MUNOSABATLARNI YUKSALTIRISH BORASIDA AMALGA OSHIRILAYOTGAN ISLOHOTLAR RIVOJI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2022.

10. Xoliqov L. The reforms and achievements in the field of interethnic harmony in Uzbekistan within the framework of the strategy of actions //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021.

11. Xoliqov L. Hamjihatlik va totuvlik fazilatlarini shakllantirishda oilaning roli //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021.

12. Xoliqov L. Behbudiyning mlliy ma'naviyatimizni yuksaltirishda tutgan o'rni //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021.

13. Xoliqov L. O'zbekistonda yoshlar migratsiyasi va bu boradagi islohotlar //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 8.

14. Xoliqov L. МЕЖНАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ СОГЛАСИЕ-ЗАЛОГ СПРАВЕДЛИВОЙ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2022. – Т. 21. – №. 21.

15. Xoliqov L. MILLATLARARO TOTUVLIK-TINCH VA TOTUV HAYOTIMIZ ROYDEVORI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 8.

16. Sobirovich T. B. Spirituality and its Need for Human Life //" ONLINE-CONFERENCE" PLATFORM. – 2021. – С. 19-21.
17. Turdiyev B. CONFUCIUS'S VIEWS ON SPIRITUAL RENEWAL //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 6. – №. 6.
18. Turdiyev B. Spiritual Renewal: THE new decree and the strategy of life-inspiring reforms //Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 6. – №. 6.
19. Turdiyev B. BUKHARA-CENTER OF ISLAMIC SPIRITUAL AND CULTURE //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 6. – №. 6.
20. Turdiyev B. Behbudi's views on the spiritual renewal of society //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 5. – №. 5.